

Python in Heliophysics Community Spring 2023 Meeting

Meeting materials are located at <http://heliopython.org/meetings/>

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Participants

76 people registered to participate in the hybrid Spring 2023 meeting via the meeting's Google sign up form. Of those 76 people, approximately 10-15 participants attended in-person, with the rest participating via the Zoom. Meeting participants' home institutions (as indicated by responses to the Google sign up form) included the following:

- NASA Goddard Space Flight Center
- Center for Astrophysics | Harvard & Smithsonian
- LASP
- Southwest Research Institute
- University of New Hampshire
- NMSU
- National Institute for Space Research, Brazil
- University of Oulu, Finland
- University of Turku
- CU Boulder CIRES/NOAA SWPC
- CU Boulder
- SSL - UC Berkeley
- University of Alabama in Huntsville
- Johns Hopkins University Applied Physics Laboratory
- Predictive Science
- United States Naval Academy
- High Altitude Observatory
- ESAC
- Community Coordinated Modeling Center, NASA Goddard Space Flight Center
- Common Action/CfHA
- National Institute for Space Research (INPE), Brazil
- NASA JPL
- National & Kapodistrian University of Athens
- Universidad de Santiago de Chile
- Polyneme LLC
- University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA)
- Stoneris
- GSFC 672 / ADNET Systems
- George Mason University
- University of Delaware
- Wright State University
- School of Space Research, KyungHee University, South Korea

- National Solar Observatory
- NASA Scientific Visualization Studio

Meeting Overview

The Spring 2023 meeting was spread over a three-day period, where each day ran approximately from 9 AM to 5 PM (slight fluctuations to accommodate delays in start time). The meeting took place in Boulder, CO at LASP's LSTB building. As with prior meetings, the meeting organizing committee chose to use the Zoom platform for the hybrid component, as Zoom is familiar to PyHC members (it is already in use for the bi-weekly PyHC telecons), it consistently provides good quality video and sound, and it lends itself nicely to large group video calls and breakout rooms. All sessions except for the Unconferences and Hackathons were recorded and uploaded to the PyHC's YouTube ([see link here](#)), with videos uploaded to [the meeting web page](#) at the end of the meeting. All presentation slides were collected and put into the [Presentations folder](#) on the meeting's Google Drive.

The meeting began Tuesday, May 16th, and ran through Thursday, May 18th. Content of each day was as follows:

- Day 1: Core project updates, other PyHC project updates, with discussions on Geomagnetic Field Models within Heliophysics, as well as the PyHC Executable Paper: the science version.
- Day 2: Tutorials (geomagnetic datacubes, HelioCloud (the basics and recent updates), package Submission to PyHC, and a clean code refresher), followed by unconference sessions on 1) running on the cloud/cloud enabling, maintainer burnout, and proposal development.
- Day 3: presentation on "Heliophysics ScienceCore curriculum development with emphasis on knowledge representation techniques to increase usability of NASA cloud-based datasets" - An overview and where PyHC fits in, as well as presentations/discussions surrounding a pyOpenSci intro, ChatGPT and PyHC, PyHC's TESS '24 solar eclipse event, and wrap up. An optional hackathon session took place after the meeting adjourned officially, in the afternoon.

Core Packages Updates

HAPI

HAPI v3.2 will better accommodate more descriptive metadata and easier access to those metadata, including coordinate system information. Another new feature coming in version 3.2 is to support serving links as one way to serve images, but this is not recommended in general. The

stated preference is for HAPI servers to serve data in a standard format, not links to data files. However, the SIAP (Simple Image Access Protocol) IVOA standard allows for this and is shown to be an effective approach (Dowler et al. 2016). HAPI would like to expand to serve coordinate transformation matrices and offer file format conversions, better visualizations and possibly search capabilities through various interfaces built on top of HAPI servers. Additionally, the related data adapters project needs about 20% more funding to be completed. Jon V. also noted a potential to include data cleaning as a separate service on top of HAPI servers.

While these capabilities are exciting, I have some concerns about the visualization comment. HAPI's primary purpose is to serve data in standard formats to the community through a standard API. Serving data carries with it a community expectation of quick-look visualizations, not necessarily high quality or complex visualizations as in many analysis workflows, but at least enough for a cursory look. The current visualization methods in HAPI are sufficient for this, although some improvement is warranted compared to today's standards. Such improvement could be an update to a more interactive visualization approach, such as that already built on top of HAPI elsewhere by Eelco Doornbus and the new iSWA HAPI cygnet, possibly even by collaborating with such a project. While some improvement in visualization is warranted, higher quality and more complex visualizations belong in the analysis packages for each data type, such as pySPEDAS, Kamodo and others - not in HAPI. In those cases, HAPI and similar services should serve as the 'plumbing' to get data into those more complex visualization routines. Feedback from a HAPI package lead confirms the two-pronged approach described here is the approach desired.

Offering coordinate transformation matrices through HAPI is one reasonable way to offer a complex capability through a website, an API, and into multiple PyHC packages. If coordinate transformations for both scalars and vectors are offered through both a website interface and a HAPI server, as HAPI does for data, then that approach could circumvent the current requirement of installing multiple packages to convert from one coordinate system to another and utilize cloud systems to speed up the necessary calculations (especially for vector conversions). For example, at least three packages are currently required to convert a satellite trajectory from the teme coordinate system available through AstroPy to the SM coordinate system available in SpacePy as an access point to a model-specific coordinate system available in Kamodo before interpolating through modeled data. This is not only a lot to expect of a science user, but is a significant barrier due to the combined installation difficulties of those packages. Additionally, no vector conversion capabilities are offered in PyHC, except possibly for conversions contained in AstroPy. Offering coordinate transformations as a service on top of HAPI appears to be a good way forward to lowering the complex software interdependency barrier.

There is a grassroots effort starting up to define what those coordinate transformation matrices should be, which is led by Robert Weigel with participation from several others in the community (STCT?). The matrix definitions determined by that group should be made available through multiple methods (e.g. API/HAPI and a website interface) and incorporated into a coordinate conversion software package as aligning with the PyHC standards, which should also be served through a website interface and API.

Infrastructure resources would also benefit from collaborating with HAPI. For example, a deeper collaboration between SPDF and HAPI would increase the number of datasets available through HAPI, thus making more datasets easily accessible, could avoid the work of developing custom APIs, and to streamline user access to the data through various analysis packages, especially since most PyHC packages use HAPI to ingest data to some extent. This ties into possible components of PyHC's long-term vision briefly discussed in the last section of this document.

An interesting item to note here is that since most PyHC packages already use HAPI to ingest data, HAPI could be used as an interface between packages for interoperability (e.g. pulling data from SpacePy into Kamodo and back), but that capability would require automatic launching of dynamic HAPI servers, which have not been developed yet. Additionally, SunPy does not (currently) use HAPI to ingest data, but instead uses fido, so interoperability with SunPy will need to be performed through fido.

PlasmaPy

The leader of the PlasmaPy package, Nick Murphy, has become a recognized resource in the community to teach good coding practices in a congenial manner. He would be a great person to fund to lead general classes for the community, such as 'How to use GitHub for beginners', general python programming, and software development resources for the community. These efforts would be great to build an entry path into software development in Heliophysics, and it should be coordinated with currently-existing summer schools on the topic.

PlasmaPy is currently funded by NSF and will pursue funding from DOE.

SunPy

SunPy is by far the most advanced python package in PyHC with multiple affiliated packages, a vibrant community, and mature software. However, even SunPy needs funding to continue advancing its capabilities (e.g. better support for multi-dimensional data and documentation refactoring), even to advance beyond Python into an analysis environment approach (e.g. a website/GUI interface).

One important question that was discussed is how to preserve SolarSoft's capabilities outside of IDL, likely into a SunPy affiliated package. One such package has a beginning on the task (XRTPy), but the effort is much larger than can be done in someone's spare time and needs funding. AI tools could aid in converting from IDL into Python, but developers are needed to finish the conversion and test for accurate performance.

SpacePy

This package is known for how problematic it is to install the thing. This difficulty arises from the FORTRAN and C routines it includes for coordinate conversions and field-line tracing for BATS-R-US data. SpacePy would greatly benefit from funding to address installation issues and overhaul their documentation. PyOpenSci (later) will be a great resource in the installation puzzle. Using SpacePy as a 'test package' in the collaboration between PyOpenSci and PyHC would be a great learning example on how that interface can work.

Pysat

Advancements in the pysat package are generally driven by user contribution in the ITM domain and generally include cleaning routines for ITM observational data. However, some new capabilities were demonstrated, including bin-averaging and a way to graphically represent when observed and modeled data are both available. The presentation given was almost identical to that for the last few years. Is this package becoming stale? Should other ITM cleaning routines be incorporated into pysat, or should pysat's capabilities be built into SPDF's website?

Kamodo

This package is a NASA open source software package, which was mentioned as a barrier instead of a positive property. If being a NASA open source software package is so restricting, then that needs to be communicated with NASA HQ and dealt with promptly. Another complexity mentioned is Kamodo's close ties to CCMC. Perhaps pressure is needed to implement Kamodo in several use-cases external to CCMC to work out what that relationship needs to be, such as using Kamodo as 'plumbing' to get more modeled data into SWxTREC's more advanced visualizations, or offering modeled data interpolated with Kamodo through HAPI from multiple institutions (e.g. JPL, LANL, APL, SWPC, etc).

PySPEDAS

PySPEDAS is the growing python version of SPEDAS, an IDL code. This package is pushing towards GUI interfaces for visualizations, which is a great example of where such development

needs to aim for. I have seen such interfaces from Kamodo-core, but not from Kamodo-ccmc or other PyHC packages. Giving funding to PySPEDAS to push this boundary would be a great way to push the PyHC packages towards that goal. This package's contributors (e.g. Jim Lewis) would be a great resource for converting SolarSoft into Python or some other free language.

Other packages and efforts

- Geo coordinate conversion tools are available in ApexPy, AACGMV2, and OCBpy specifically for high latitudes (Angeline Burrell). Those packages should be part of the coordinate conversion conversation at DASH and the working group led by Robert (Bob) Weigel.
- CCSDSpy (Daniel de Silva) has been used by several missions to process binary spacecraft data in the cclds data format. Supported by mission institutions (e.g. JPL).
- Alec Engell presented on streamlining data analysis on the cloud, but the file format is Zarr. Packages used included Bokeh, fsspec and kerchunk. Later discussion on software operation on cloud data pointed to fsspec as a possible common-ground for PyHC packages.
- XRTPy (Joy Velasquez): Working on converting part of SolarSoft into Python. This and other similar efforts to convert pieces of SolarSoft into Python need to be pushed forward, mentored and accelerated by community involvement and funding to preserve those capabilities.
- HelioCloud (Sandy Antunes) is a maturing platform for the PyHC community to test software capabilities on the cloud and for science analyses.
- Discussion started on a standard for hosting geomagnetic field models (e.g. Tsyganenko, IGRF, etc) in Python packages in PyHC. Discussion concluded that the interface to all of these models should be the same and return the same thing - the magnetic field (e.g. same component order?). Could imitate (or build into) the VIRES magnetic field visualization tool where users can switch between magnetic field models via a drop-down list. Want the pieces underneath such a surface to be standardized in ways that ensure efficiency and speed. We need to ensure this conversation continues, possibly in PyHC telecons or dedicated sessions at later PyHC meetings or related conferences (e.g. GEM, TESS, AGU).

Valuable Collaborations

- Donny Winston presented his funded TOPST work to build Heliophysics Open Science resources. PyHC can be a great resource for this by contributing pieces of tutorials to

example workflows and analyses. Since this work can be done via honorarium, collaborating with the TOPST effort can also easily plug into the current need to develop PyHC multi-package tutorials for the PyHC Gallery (two results with one effort).

- Leah Wasser presented on the PyOpenSci group, which offers a free peer-review service for open science software (not just open-source). Conversations on previous PyHC telecons agreed that PyHC packages should be officially reviewed for both their alignment with good software practices and with the PyHC standards, but no one volunteered to do this since the work is extensive. Collaborating with PyOpenSci looks like an ideal way to tackle this problem. Membership in PyHC could require all members to assist PyOpenSci in the review of at least one other package, and PyHC leadership could assess each submitted package based solely on its alignment with the PyHC standards (on top of the standard review). A big plus here is that the packages can then be easily approved in JOSS (the Journal of Open Source Software) AND get PyOpenSci and PyHC badges on their repositories. This process could easily be required as an open science requirement for HTM proposals. Another plus is that the PyOpenSci review process checks for redundancy of capability among packages, which is expected to increase collaboration between packages in the community and across domains.
 - leah@pyopensci.org

Open Science Session (end of Day 1)

- Rebecca Ringuette and Gretchen Gueguen (OSF) paired up to lead a session on open science, the PyHC executable paper, and PyHC's role in the push towards open science. The session spent about half the time outlining the three topics and half the time on discussing them. The discussion was lively at times, attesting to the community's willing involvement in such activities. Four main questions were considered in the discussion, hosted on a miro board (<https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMKYw40w=/>):
 - (1) What PyHC software changes are needed to better support the open science experiment? Which of these need funding?
 - (2) How can PyHC better advertise data access and analysis support in PyHC packages?
 - (3) How can PyHC help with accessibility issues for modeled data?
 - (4) How can PyHC prepare for, collaborate with, and enable the next generation of infrastructures?
- Some common threads in the answers to these questions include:
 - Community desire to have easy ways to install and run PyHC packages (pip install, containerized, etc), avoid package dependency conflicts, and have a referenceable (e.g. with a DOI) environment with a release schedule (yearly) coordinated with other community package releases available in multiple ways

(pip install PyHC, conda-forge, and containers). Progress on this was made in a hackathon on the last day of the meeting.

- Recognition that PyHC packages need to run seamlessly on data downloaded to the users machine, data hosted on the cloud, and data retrieved through HAPI/fido. This was discussed further in an unconference session on the second day. Also need to easily/automatically adapt to a broad range of hardware infrastructures (e.g. GPUs and systems with a large number of cores/processors).
- The lacking discoverability and community knowledge of PyHC packages. Some suggested ways to address this include DOIs for all packages (and requiring them to be cited in publications and websites), improved search capability on the PyHC website (possibly by adding SPASE metadata records) and links from the archives to notebooks related to a given dataset.
- In a related collection of comments, funding for an army of tutors was requested. This army of tutors would use a (yet to be generated) set of standard single and multi-package tutorials to give tutorials for community at the PyHC summer school, tutorial sessions and booths at various conferences, virtual office hours, and other outreach opportunities (e.g. classes hosted at institutions/agencies). These tutorials could be sourced from the growing PyHC gallery, PyHC summer school materials, and package documentation. Honoraria should be given for original (and useful) contributions outside of pre-existing materials.
- Other requests could be handled by a partnership with PyOpenSci, such as guidance on how to include scripts in other languages in a package build, metrics on package usefulness, and improvements on documentation.
- The remaining requests can be viewed at the link to the miro board above. Screenshots of the contributed comments are included in the two figures below.

Figure 1: Contributed comments for Questions 1 and 2.

Figure 2: Contributed comments for Questions 3 and 4.

Unconference Results

Overall notes by Rebecca Ringuette: the group (both in-person and virtual) made good progress in planning the next steps for running on data in the cloud by choosing fsspec as a possible way forward, and some great conversations occurred for burnout. The burnout conversation naturally progressed to a proposed solution: adding backup people to proposals and/or smooth out funding across smaller institutions (multi-institutional alliances?).

Running on the Cloud/Cloud Enabling

Main topic ideas

- PyHC projects operating in the cloud (data not on local filesystem w/o writing access in everything)
- Run PyHC packages on data in S3
 - Files are a “GET” request; will occasionally fail to download due to only 99.9% availability
 - Object store, not a file system
- Users should be aware of where files are, but not have to worry about implementing it
 - easy to learn, hard to master (should be the goal)
- How much does fsspec solve? It abstracts local, S3, ftp, etc. Does it work with astropy/FITS, xarray, HDF5, CDF, netCDF3?
 - netCDF3 not supported by HDF5 so experiments needed
- Can packages that currently accept filenames also be made to accept file-like objects or fsspec file handles?
 - We’d want to vet the API to make sure it’s something we can live with (even if it stops being supported?)
- Getting a handle on cloud costing is key
- EBS is different than EFS (EFS = no cost if empty, EBS = constant cost) and instance store is fast but potentially costly (?)
- Talk to Earth Science, OpenDAP people who solved this 5 years ago, find their lessons learned (via James Gallagher, Nathan Potter, see this page: <https://www.opendap.org/about/engineering>)
- EC2 pricing table showing different types of storage for different instances types:
 - <https://aws.amazon.com/ec2/pricing/on-demand/>
- Cdflib (pure python): already supports s3 or http paths; netcdf4 does not, but there is a package S3netCDF4 which supports this. But maybe additional support for specifying inputs via fsspec would be a good idea.

Whiteboard:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1L35Cu2MHx3Ta6Lf9L1RYNHpiFRAI6p1q/view?usp=share_link

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1L5Kzun9ZSxeGY3QqR1ADI6gQvijb-OWn/view?usp=share_link

Actions:

- Rebecca & Sandy: look into fsspec and how it might help with FITS, CDF, NetCDF3, NetCDF4/HDF
- Marcin: write up his AWS optimization/cheats for effective caching on real problems and storage strategies in general. (play with Heliocloud, maybe the instance storage is there already, then we could experiment locally)
- Jon V.: reach out to James Gallagher etc on cloud transition, particularly how they handled temporary scratch

Maintainer Burnout

- General thoughts before starting
 - Do not share personal experiences from this session... confidentiality is key.
 - Step up and step back.
- Define burnout and the types of burnout
 - NASA talk on this recently
 - Slides:
 - Beginning stage: need a break and then fine
 - Late stage: don't care anymore and a break doesn't help
- Actionable ways to reverse burnout:
 - 15 min occasional presentations on burnout?
 - These kinds of meetings can be helpful to energize (especially live meetings), especially after the Pandemic years
 - Call outs to people for work done at meetings?
 - People that tend to talk first at these meetings are more extroverts/ambiverts... introverts still want to be heard, too.
 - But these meetings also leave people with more (unfunded) work to do... this community in general overloads people (lack of good boundaries)
 - Connect to things you value in general, work on things you enjoy, and feel you're making a difference
 - What validates us at work? Not being funded makes work feel invalidated. Mental health often times correlates to funding situation.
- Work-life balance:

- Article: 'greatest gen' worked to survive, boomers & gen-X worked to raise their standard of living, gen-Z+ work to improve their quality of life.
 - And the millennials? :P
- Fatigue = dealing w/ customers. Translating ideas into code. This field has a lot of customer-facing work.
- What about leadership / personal management / management courses at the front end of PyHC meetings? (perhaps starting something the day *prior* to the meeting starting officially)
 - Or structure the meeting so that there are enough breaks for people to go for walks, have longer talks, etc
 - From Julie: yes! I agree! Next meeting we will prioritize that more.
- Psychological safety
 - Ask q's w/o shame for it. Bring true / authentic self into the room.
 - Marginalized groups deal w/ extra overhead in terms of how they present themselves, etc. that can increase burnout risk.
 - Affirmations help!
- Workplace idea: Volunteer Amnesty Day, where people can say "I won't be continuing doing this"
- Academia funnels everyone into the same pipe, w/ a lack of release valves
 - Lack of job security if you don't get funded... what to do then?
 - "The Heliophysics Proposal and Soft Money Guild" - share proposal ideas/opps/leftover funds if you don't have the time, but think another would be a great fit?
 - Ideas relevant to NASA TOPS? Should we contact them?
 - Ability to float proposal stuff depends on whether you're correctly plugged into professional networks
 - Some institutions don't let the money float out once it's in.
 - Float the rich years into the lean years
 - Obligated to keep groups funded simply because they've existed?

Proposal Development

- Proposal Development
 - Ask to be on reviewer panels
 - NSPIRES
 - Ask Reiner
- Funding
 - Models for funding in the future (e.g. PyHC leadership activities)
 - Data and computing working group is needed in heliophysics to guide decisions

- Focus on publication efforts... a metric that is valued by headquarters. RSEs should be more on par with scientists, which requires publishing s/w in open source journals. “See, our community helps build the tools AND we generate more papers”.
- Proposal opportunities:
 - https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1IYhvN3s2zJySdSCjSlgf_DOSauA8W7jRVhZ9oupozPE/edit#gid=0
- <https://www.simonsfoundation.org/grant/scientific-software-research-faculty-award/?tab=how-to-apply>

Hackathon Results

PyHC Virtual Environment

On the last day of the PyHC Spring 2023 meeting, Shawn led a hackathon centered around trying to create one Python virtual environment that has every PyHC package installed. Roughly ten people participated in total, with three of them participating remotely. At the start of the hackathon, Shawn presented a spreadsheet he had previously generated which showed allowable version ranges of 250+ packages that the ~60 PyHC packages depend on. The group condensed the requirements into one "requirements.txt" file that could be pip installed. The file was then uploaded to a new GitHub repository (<https://github.com/sapols/pyhc-environment-files/tree/main>) and the group coordinated their development around that repo for the rest of the hackathon. A second requirements file was made to automate the (attempted) installation of the latest versions of all the PyHC packages. To the group's pleasant surprise, the pip installs worked on the first try, proving that the generated version ranges in Shawn's initial spreadsheet were valid. An "import-test.py" file was added to the repo which runs import statements for every PyHC package before printing a success message. This script did not succeed on anyone's machine on the first try, for various reasons, so the rest of the hackathon centered around fixing environment issues to get the script to succeed on as many different machines as time allowed. Windows machines proved problematic, but by the end of the hackathon, Shawn and a couple others were able to successfully run "import-test.py" on their Macs. We consider this hackathon a success because of that. We successfully created a Python virtual environment that was capable of importing every single PyHC package for the first time ever. This was a milestone moment for PyHC. Future work will involve making this environment as portable as possible so that anyone can use it.

Comment by Rebecca Ringuette: great progress was made in the Thursday afternoon hackathon on creating a single reference Python environment where most (if not all) PyHC packages

successfully installed. Previous work on this resulted in the PyHC 2022 summer school container (<https://gallery.ecr.aws/q3h7b4o8/helio-notebook-pyhc>), but was limited in the number of packages included. One such environment was created on Shawn Polson's computer. Additionally, the in-person members of the Kamodo and SpacePy packages collaborated on improving their installation methods across operating systems (including Windows).

Improving Sideways Interoperability

One hackathon session focused on improving sideways interoperability between xrtpy, aiapy, emtoolkit, and other other PyHC packages. In particular, the participants discussed ways to make a common object to represent temperature response functions across packages, and developed some prototypes. The participants of this hackathon were Joy Velasquez, Nick Murphy, & Jonathan Slavin from xrtpy, Joe Plowman from emtoolkit, and Will Barnes from sunpy and aiapy.

Comment by Rebecca Ringuette: in parallel, some progress was also made towards a common interface for creating temperature responses for instruments. Work needs to be continued, possibly funded.

General Meeting Notes

- Notable lack of AI/ML capabilities in the packages, possibly due to lack of PyHC advertisement in those communities.
- Community agreed to have a third category on the PyHC project page: (Unevaluated, Confirmed, and Core). Unanimous agreement to remove the Python 3 column and replace with a 'Latest Update' column (or similar) as a measure of whether the package is still 'alive'.
- Classes on software basics (clean software practices and building a package) and tutorials (e.g. Pangeo in Heliophysics) were reasonably well-received. Should possibly be delegated to the summer school, though, to reach the intended audience.
- The unconference format was a great success! Attendees submitted and voted upon possible discussion topics before the dedicated sessions. The top few were chosen and discussed during the unconference sessions, and the remaining ones were delegated to upcoming telecons.
- AI technology is almost advanced enough to develop a PyHC chat bot to help visitors discover PyHC package capabilities and create code snippets. Shawn worries (unnecessarily) that AI will soon replace him, but someone still needs to keep the AI straight. Unanimous agreement that a beta version of the PyHC chat bot, when ready, should be made available to those interested (not the public).

- Despite the Heliophysics community's excitement about the upcoming solar eclipse (during TESS), very few in PyHC were eager to collaborate on a PyHC project to serve real-time data in a display at TESS (likely because of the funding issue). Part of the motivation is to get real-time capabilities into PyHC packages, but few seemed interested. Kamodo (modeled data), iSWA (CCMC) and HAPI (APL) were the exceptions to this. If HAPI can get funding to serve real-time data, then many PyHC packages should be able to easily use that interface to incorporate real-time data into their visualization. **PyHC leadership needs to follow up with those efforts to outline what can be done and to ensure timely progress.** Agreed that it would be ideal to show some data sources that change with time during the eclipse and some that don't.
- The issue of long term code permanence came up. Two mentioned ways to achieve this is to ensure the code runs on many systems now so it can run on some systems later (e.g. pip install works on Linux, Mac and Windows - already a PyHC standard), move codes in licensed languages to free ones (e.g. IDL to Python), and to move towards code-free interfaces (e.g. GUIs). Unit tests are critical in the language transition process. SolarSoft and SPEDAS (both IDL packages) need support/funding to make this transition. Can AI tools be used to speed up this process? GUI implementation can be made reproducible by allowing users to download a script encoding the user's selections.
- PyHC representation in the Frontiers of Astronomy and Space Sciences: Snakes on a Spaceship was good. Do something similar every few years? Next time, include a paper on advances in PyHC (e.g. summer school, reference environment, community involvement, etc).

Improving PyHC (meetings and overall)

- Some of the core package presentations were too similar to previous presentations. We could address this by asking package presentations to give a short description, an update, and to describe one or more current challenges for that package. Some already loosely used this format, but it would be ideal for all the core packages to do this. This approach is also expected to promote better discussions.
- We need to have some discussion time after each core presentation is completed to brainstorm on the stated problem, and a net discussion time after all core presentations are completed to discuss broader issues (e.g. advancing our packages' interoperability, ideas for collaborations, overlaps in development goals, etc).
- A conversation coming up at DASH aims to make progress on interoperability between PyHC packages, particularly for coordinate conversions. Would be good to pinpoint similar areas in PyHC packages where interoperability could be improved to encourage similar future sessions (e.g. unit conversions), and consider hosting those capabilities on the HDRL website (e.g. a coordinate conversion webpage). Although visualization is a

tempting choice, the visualizations standard for each domain are unique enough to keep the capabilities separate in the packages.

- One idea to deepen PyHC's integration into infrastructure is to collaborate with infrastructure entities (e.g. SPDF, SDAC, interested academic institutions and laboratories, etc) to use PyHC packages to satisfy open science requirements for their data (e.g. data access through HAPI/fido, or a new option for higher quality quick-look plots through an embedded GUI developed by the package) instead of infrastructure entities (new and current) developing these capabilities independently. Can Python versions of popular tools be created (e.g. pyAutoPlot) and included in PyHC?
- Another way to deepen PyHC's role in the community is to act on the suggestion to create an army of paid PyHC trainers (see the Open Science Session section). This team will act as PyHC representatives at various conferences and schools to teach the community how to use the various PyHC packages to perform analyses relevant to each domain. This could be funded by the current push for open science (NSF, NASA and others) and by collaborating with other educational efforts (e.g. NASA's HEAT and SCoPE programs, <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/heat/home/> and <https://science.nasa.gov/science-activation-team/smd-community-of-practice-for-education>). Original and useful contributions to their tutorial materials should be compensated appropriately by PyHC using a new added section of their budget. These tutors need to have a dedicated (and paid) training session led by PyHC software developers and leadership staff to properly prepare them for these responsibilities. Successful completion of this training should result in a special 'PyHC Trainer' badge that should be worn at conferences (e.g. a polo with the logo and related text or a pin/hat/something).
- Encouraging PyHC packages to develop GUIs (code-free interfaces) could lead to a PyHC analysis website in collaboration with HelioCloud and HDRL. See VEDA (<https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/dashboard/>) for how this is being done in Earth Science. Developing this in Heliophysics with PyHC would be a great community resource and would deepen PyHC's permanence in the Heliophysics Community. We could include preliminary work towards this in a 5-year vision, but additional funding for GUI/UI/UX and website development will be needed. One way to work towards this goal would be for honorarium to be made available to Heliophysics community members to contribute quality multi-package tutorials to the PyHC Gallery (subject to review by PyHC leadership and representatives from the software packages included in the tutorials). Those tutorials could then be used to design a website interface to accomplish the same analysis through a website hosted by HelioCloud (see below).
- It will be advantageous for infrastructure resources such as SPDF to collaborate with PyHC to advance our infrastructure capabilities for datasets by streamlining user access to the data through analysis packages. Such access could be added to the dataset entries on the search result pages by simply adding a link on that entry titled 'Analyze with

pySPEDAS' or the appropriate package for the dataset, which will lead to a webpage interface hosting various analysis capabilities powered by that package (e.g. VEDA (<https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/dashboard/>), Brian Freitag: brian.m.freitag@nasa.gov), but for Heliophysics). Until the GUI version of those analyses methods are developed, the link can instead either lead to a static notebook tutorial hosted on PyHC's website or an executable version of the same notebook on HelioCloud (with a limit on compute).

- Need to add more open science ideas, recommendations for various interested parties (e.g. NASA, commercial, mission groups, educators, etc) and a vision to move forward, including specific tasks to focus on in the next year, 5 years, etc. in a future meeting report.

Next Steps

- The DASH conference is in October of this year, with many PyHC members leading sessions.
- No spring meeting next year due to the PyHC summer school next year. Need to determine a good timeline for planning (both the logistics and the material).
- Fall PyHC meeting will be virtual, possibly delayed into early next year (February?). Or, we will combine at the DASH meeting.
- Unconference topics not discussed will be telecon topics in the near future. (List on slide.)
- DASH/IHDEA meetings in early October.
- PyHC has a scheduled poster session at the upcoming AGU 2023 meeting in San Francisco, CA, "SH012-I. Implementations in Python for Solar and Space Physics Poster". Time and date during the meeting TBA.

References

Dowler, P., D. Tody and F. Bonnarel (2016). IVOA Simple Image Access. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1601.00519> and <https://www.ivoa.net/documents/SIA/>

Final agenda

	Start Time (MDT)	End Time (MDT)	Duration (min)	Type	Title	Presenter/Discussion Lead
Tuesday, May 16						
Tue, May 16, 23	9:15	9:20	0:05	Presentation	Introductions, welcome, meeting goals	Julie Barnum
Tue, May 16, 23	9:20	9:40	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: HAPI</i>	Jon V.
Tue, May 16, 23	9:40	10:00	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: PlasmaPy</i>	Nick M.
Tue, May 16, 23	10:00	10:20	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: SunPy</i>	Will B.
Tue, May 16, 23	10:20	10:47	0:27		Break	
Tue, May 16, 23	10:47	11:07	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: SpacePy</i>	Jon N
Tue, May 16, 23	11:07	11:27	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: pysat</i>	Russell S
Tue, May 16, 23	11:27	11:47	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: Kamodo</i>	Darren D.Z.
Tue, May 16, 23	11:47	12:07	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: PySPEDAS</i>	Jim L.
Tue, May 16, 23	12:07	13:15	1:08		Lunch	
Tue, May 16, 23	13:15	13:35	0:20	Presentation	<i>Geomagnetic and high latitude coordinate tools</i>	Angeline Burrell
Tue, May 16, 23	13:35	13:55	0:20	Presentation	<i>XRTpy intro</i>	Joy Velasquez
Tue, May 16, 23	13:55	14:15	0:20	Presentation	CCSDSPy intro	Daniel E. da Silva
Tue, May 16, 23	14:15	14:35	0:20	Presentation	HITS update	Alec Engell
Tue, May 16, 23	14:35	14:50	0:15	Discussion	<i>Further subdividing PyHC Projects</i>	Shawn Polson/Julie Barnum
Tue, May 16, 23	14:50	15:00	0:10		Break	
Tue, May 16, 23	15:00	16:00	1:00	Discussion	<i>Geomagnetic Field Models within Heliophysics</i>	Ashley Smith (and others)
Tue, May 16, 23	16:00	17:30	1:30	Discussion	<i>PyHC Executable Paper: the science version</i>	Rebecca Ringuette

Wednesday, May 17						
Wed, May 17, 23	9:00	9:30	0:30	Tutorial	Geomagnetic datacubes	Ashley Smith
Wed, May 17, 23	9:30	10:15	0:45	Tutorial	HelioCloud (the basics and recent updates)	Brian Thomas et al.
Wed, May 17, 23	10:15	11:10	0:55	Tutorial	Package Submission to PyHC	Shawn Polson
Wed, May 17, 23	11:10	11:25	0:15		Break	
Wed, May 17, 23	11:25	11:55	0:30	Tutorial	Clean code refresher	Nick Murphy
Wed, May 17, 23	11:55	12:10	0:15	Discussion	Unconference voting/organizing	
Wed, May 17, 23	12:10	13:25	1:15		Lunch	
Wed, May 17, 23	13:25	14:40	1:15	Unconference	Unconference Sessions	
				Topic 1	Running on the cloud/cloud enabling	
Wed, May 17, 23	14:40	14:55	0:15		Break	
Wed, May 17, 23	14:40	15:55	1:15	Unconference	Unconference Sessions	
				Topic 2	Maintainer burnout	
				Topic 3	Proposal development?	
Wed, May 17, 23	15:55	16:10	0:15	Discussion	Unconference summaries	
Wed, May 17, 23	16:10	16:40	0:30	Discussion	Hackathon Planning	
Wed, May 17, 23	19:00				Group Dinner at Rio Grande on Walnut Street	
Thursday, May 18						
Thu, May 18, 23	9:10	9:40	0:30	Presentation/Discussion	"Heliophysics ScienceCore curriculum development with emphasis on knowledge representation techniques to increase usability of NASA cloud-based datasets" - An overview and where PyHC fits in	Donny Winston
Thu, May 18, 23	9:40	10:10	0:30	Presentation	pyOpenSci intro	Leah Wasser
Thu, May 18, 23	10:10	11:10	1:00	Presentation/Discussion	ChatGPT and PyHC	Shawn Polson

Thu, May 18, 23	11:10	11:55	0:45	Discussion	PyHC's TESS '24 Solar Eclipse Event	Shawn Polson
Thu, May 18, 23	11:55	12:10	0:15	Discussion	Wrap Up	Julie Barnum
			Optiona l Hackat hon Afterno on			
Thu, May 18, 23	12:00	17:00	5:00	Hackathon	Hackathon Session (Optional)	